

CORNER BOLTED STEEL-TO-CONCRETE END-PLATE CONNECTIONS EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL INVESTIGATIONS UNDER BIAXIAL BENDING

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ABSTRACT

In the past decades, steel frame design has traditionally overlooked the critical structure-joint interaction, particularly for steel-to-concrete connections. Despite extensive research on steel-to-steel connections, there exists a significant research gap concerning corner bolted steel-to-concrete end-plate connections subjected to biaxial bending moments, with no existing code provisions for the latter. As such, the present study comprises four full-scale experimental tests to assess the behaviour of corner bolted steel-to-concrete end-plate connections subjected to uniaxial and biaxial bending moments. A particular attention is dedicated to the impact of the moment orientation on the initial rotational stiffness, failure modes, and bending resistances. In addition, a non-linear finite element model was developed and validated against experimental results to gain insights into linear, non-linear behaviours and contact pressure distributions. Key findings include the generation of prying effect, leading to concrete crushing at the plate's edge, anchor bolt failure, crack formation in welds at flange tips, and yielding of bottom and tip-top flanges. The centre of compression proposed by Eurocode is found to be shallow and over-conservative, significantly impacting stiffness and resistance. These findings provide a critical starting point to propose design provisions for stiffness and resistance of corner bolted steel-to-concrete end-plate connections under biaxial bending moment.

Keywords: Corner bolt, steel-to-concrete end-plate connection, biaxial bending moment.

1 INTRODUCTION

The study of steel-to-concrete connections holds crucial importance, especially in the nuclear sector, where these connections play a vital role in carrying the metal supports of pipelines. However, the emergence of service defects, the evolution of stresses, and vital post-Fukushima regulatory changes make the justification of these connections quite stringent. The conservative nature of design standards, which often neglect the real and complex behaviour of connections, considering them as either hinges or fixed connections without taking into account biaxial bending moments, contributes in rather complicating the justifications for the extension of nuclear power plants' operating life. As such, there is a need to adequately understand the behaviour of these structures subjected to complex loading configurations.

In the past, research has been conducted on the behaviour of bolted steel-to-concrete end-plate connections subjected to bending moment and axial force. Jaspart & Vandegans (1) developed an analytical method that accounts for the semi-rigidity of connections. Their work, based on experimental tests, along with that of Wald et al. (2; 3) has enriched the rules proposed by the European standard, EN1993-1-8 (4), allowing for a better understanding of their behaviour under bending moments. Drake & Elkin (5) developed analytical approaches, basis of the American standard, AISC DG1 (6), to address the same issue. Similarly, Stamatopoulos & Ermopoulos (7)

combined experimental and numerical approaches to propose an analytical method for determining the stiffness and strength of the connection. Bayer et al. (8) conducted experimental and numerical investigations on the behaviour of column bases under biaxial bending moment. Their goal was to develop a simplified numerical method to determine the bending resistance. Recently, Seco et al. (9) as well as Cloete & Roth (10) combined biaxial bending moment and axial force, using numerical simulations validated by experimental tests. The former examined configurations where the anchor bolts were located behind the flanges, while the latter explored connections with anchor bolts placed in the corners of the base-plate. These research works have significantly advanced the understanding and modelling of steel-to-concrete connections subjected to biaxial bending moment. However, a gap still exists in the literature concerning the position of the centre of compression especially as concerns corner-bolted steel-to-concrete end-plate connections. As such, in the present research work, four experimental tests, included in a large campaign on 26 specimens, were performed until failure. The purpose was to investigate the influence of the bending moment angle on several critical aspects of the structural connection. This research aimed to evaluate its effect on the stiffness, failure modes, and strength of corner bolted steel-to-concrete end-plate connections. Moreover, by complementing the experimental program with numerical analyses, the specific objective was to gain insights into the position of the centre of compression in the compressive area of the connection.

2 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

2.1 Overview

The objective of this experimental program was to test steel-to-concrete end-plate connections under monotonic loading in both directions separately, and then simultaneously. The experimental setup featured a reinforced concrete block, with dimensions of 770×900×1450 mm. 1370×690 mm HA 12 and 140×690 mm HA 10 stirrups were placed along support zones to prevent concrete cone and shear failure. This reinforcement was complemented by an ST 25C steel mesh, above and below the stirrups to prevent side-face blow-out. As shown in *Fig. 1*, the steel-to-concrete connection consisted of an HEB 200 beam fixed to the concrete block by four M22 anchor bolts, at 405 mm depth, with a 400×400×15 mm end-plate. These bolts were anchored using 70×70×20 mm plates, secured by nuts positioned both above and below the plate. The connection between the steel beam and the end-plate was ensured by an 8 mm fillet weld in the flanges and 5 mm in the web designed to avoid its failure. The steel grade of plates and beams were S275 and S355, respectively. The anchor bolts were of class 4.6. The concrete class was C25/30. The concrete block was designed and reinforced so that brittle failure of the concrete would not be obtained during the transfer of tensile forces by the anchor bolts.

2.2 Test Setup

The beam was loaded by a vertical hydraulic jack (see *Fig. 1-b* and *c*). The concrete block rested on two frames. Rollers were welded with a distribution plate positioned on the concrete foundation at the level of frame B. To simplify the application of the load at the end of the beam for cases of out-of-plane and biaxial bending moments, a circular flange was used with M24 bolts class 10.9. The beam was thus divided into two parts. *Fig. 1-c* shows how the inner part in contact with the concrete block was oriented according to the applied force. The outer part was bolted to the inner part using the circular flange, and the hydraulic jack was attached to the flanges. The main geometric parameters and loading conditions are detailed in *Table 1* and depicted in *Fig. 1-b* and *c*.

Table 1 – Geometry of specimens

Specimen	Type of loading	Beam	Plate	Anchor bolt
C1-TP15-M0	In-plane bending			
C1-TP15-M90	Out-of-plane bending			
C1-TP15-M45	Bending orientation at 45°	HEB200-S355	400×400×15-S275	M22-4.6
C1-TP15-M30	Bending orientation at 30°			

The following instrumentation was implemented as seen in Fig. 2:

- Inclinometers, I_1 and I_2 , were placed on the beam and on the concrete block to measure the connection rotation.
- 8 LVDTs, V_1 to V_8 , under the beam and the concrete block, to measure the displacement of the connection and estimate its rotation.
- 4 LVDTs, U_{ti} and U_{bi} , placed horizontally at the top and bottom of the plate to measure both displacements from the concrete block and estimate the position of the neutral axis of the connection.
- 8 axial strain gauges, J_1 to J_8 , on the flanges of the beams (4 on each side) measuring the deformations of the beam near the welds.
- 4 force sensors, B_1 to B_4 , on the anchor bolts to monitor the evolution of tensile forces.
- 2 to 3 rosette strain gauges on the plate, R_1 to R_2/R_3 , near the welds at flange corner.

a)

Fig. 1 – Connections and test set-up a) Geometry of the connection; b) In-plane test set-up with specimen M0; c) Biaxial bending with specimen M45

Fig. 3 – a) Comparison of moment-rotation curves; b) Anchor bolts force distribution in specimen M45

Table 4 - Rotational stiffnesses, plastic and ultimate bending moments, yielded components and failure modes

Specimen	$S_{j,ini}$ kNm/rad	$M_{j,pl}$ kNm	$M_{j,u}$ kNm	$M_{j,pl} / M_{j,u}$ -	Components yielded						Failure mode
					TF	BF	W	C	EP	AB	
M0	4163	71.2	87.5	0.81	○	○	○	○	○	●	Failure of bolts and partial yielding of plates
M30	4207	66.1	85.7	0.77	○	○	○	○	○	●	
M45	4269	55.8	76.7	0.73	○	○	○	○	○	●	
M90	3405	52.2	66.3	0.79	○	○	○	○	○	●	

○ Yielded; ● Failure

TF – Tip-top flange; BF – Bottom flange; W – Weld; C – Concrete; EP – End-plate; AB – Anchor bolts.

Fig. 4 – Interaction curves following the angle of inclination a) Initial rotational stiffness; b) Plastic and ultimate bending moments

The experimental points are close to an elliptical curve while enveloping it, except for the plastic bending moment of the specimen inclined at 45°, as seen in Fig. 4. Fig. 5 shows the components at failure. The failure mode corresponded to anchor bolts failure in tension and partial end-plate yielding. In the tensile area, curved yield lines developed passing through the tips of the flanges. This led to the emergence of cracks in the nearby welds without causing a complete detachment. Additionally, the concrete in this area experienced crushing due to the prying force exerted by the plate. The tip-top flanges of the specimens yielded, and the lower flange yielded entirely in all specimens except M90, where yielding was limited to the flange tips.

Fig. 5 – Specimen at failure a) Concrete crushing due to prying; b) Weld cracking; c) Anchor bolt failure; d) Curved yield lines near tensed anchor bolts

3 NUMERICAL INVESTIGATIONS

3.1 Overview

The numerical modelling of steel-to-concrete connections presents significant challenges due to the intricate contact and friction interactions between components. These complexities are further heightened by the brittle nature of concrete and the steel-to-concrete contact interaction. To navigate these issues, ANSYS is used to reproduce the experimental tests through finite element modelling, providing a more detailed investigation on the behaviour of steel-to-concrete connections subjected to biaxial bending.

3.2 Finite Element Model

The components of the connections were modelled using SOLID186 elements. This hexahedral volumetric element is defined by 20 nodes with three degrees of freedom per node. Contact surfaces were modelled by using CONTACT 174 and TARGET 170 elements. The surfaces encompass contacts between:

- The anchor bolt's nut, washer and end-plate
- The anchor bolt and the holes of washers, end-plates and the concrete block
- The inner surface of the end-plate and the concrete block.

Friction at the interface between different elements was considered. An isotropic Coulomb friction law was implemented, using coefficients of 0.3 and 0.5 for steel-to-steel and steel-to-concrete contacts, respectively, following the approach used by Seco et al. (9) as well as Cloete & Roth (10). For steel components, mechanical properties from characteristic tests were used to construct both nominal and true stress-strain curves, following the proposal of Couchaux et al. (14). This included adopting an elastoplastic behaviour model based on von Mises' plasticity criterion with hardening, assuming perfect elasticity up to the yield limit, followed by elastoplastic behaviour. To enhance the model, steel fracture in anchor bolts was simulated using the Gurson model (15). This model, further refined by Needleman & Tvergaard (16), suggests that ductile metals undergo void growth, nucleation, and coalescence as plasticity develops, with increasing porosity indicating damage and a consequent reduction in load-bearing capacity. For carbon steels, specific Tvergaard constants and porosity values (initial, nucleation, critical, and failure) were adopted from Slimane et al. (17) and the ANSYS Guide (18), contingent upon the steel's mechanical properties as detailed in section 2.3. Concrete behaviour was modelled numerically using properties derived from compression tests, particularly the mean compressive strength, f_{cm} . ANSYS Microplane model was used to extract a simplified non-linear elastoplastic behaviour of concrete, that could account for localized pressure. This model uses uniaxial stress-strain laws on multiple planes, incorporates plasticity through the Drucker-Prager model with tension and compression caps, and considers damage through an

anisotropic formulation at the macroscopic level, thus capturing the material's response under all possible triaxialities. In terms of boundary conditions, displacement degrees of freedom were restrained at the bottom and lateral faces of the concrete block and at the base of the anchor bolts. For symmetry-achievable cases (M0 and M90), only half of the connection was modelled. The connection was subjected to eccentric loading by imposing a vertical displacement at the free-end nodes of the beam. *Fig. 6* shows the detailed numerical model with the material laws used for each component of the connection.

Fig. 6 – Numerical model of the typical connection

3.3 Comparison to test results

The moment-rotation curves obtained numerically and experimentally are depicted in *Fig. 7* and are quite close.

Fig. 7 – Experimental and numerical moment-rotation curves.

The experimental and numerical results for initial rotational stiffnesses, plastic and ultimate bending moments are detailed and compared in *Table 5*. The numerical model demonstrates high fidelity to experimental tests, achieving up to 98% precision for the ultimate strength of specimen M30. However, for specimen M0, a deviation of 22.1% is observed for the rotational stiffness. Despite this discrepancy, the result is deemed acceptable in terms of stiffness. The lower experimental stiffness value for M0 is likely attributable to significant end-plate imperfections due to welding not modelled here. *Fig. 8* shows that the deformations and overall behaviour of the connection in the numerical model align closely with experimental findings, validating the model's effectiveness for further numerical investigations.

Table 5 - Experimental and numerical results of the initial rotational stiffness, plastic and ultimate moments

Specimen	Experimental			Numerical			Δ		
	$S_{i,ini}$	$M_{i,pl}$	$M_{i,u}$	$S_{i,ini}$	$M_{i,pl}$	$M_{i,u}$	$S_{i,ini}$	$M_{i,pl}$	$M_{i,u}$
	kNm/rad	kNm	kNm	kNm/rad	kNm	kNm	%	%	%
M0	4163	71.2	87.5	5084	69.4	86.9	22.1	2.5	0.7
M30	4207	66.1	85.7	4136	67.2	85.5	1.7	1.7	0.2
M45	4269	55.8	76.7	4458	50.9	72.8	4.4	8.8	5.1
M90	3405	52.2	66.3	3647	49.2	69.4	7.1	5.7	4.5

Fig. 8 – Deformed shape close to failure – Plate's lateral view a) M0; b) M30; c) M45; d) M90

As observed during experimental tests, the lower flange, as well as the tip-top flange were found to numerically yield. Yield lines formed in both the tensed and compressed parts of each connection, as depicted in Fig. 9. In the tensile area, curved yield lines, similar to those observed experimentally, emerged around the anchor bolts, extending through the welds and the tip-top flanges. Notably, substantial deformations, more than 20%, were observed at the bases of the weld beads, aligning with the experimental detection of cracks in these areas. In the compressed areas of all specimens except M90, another yield line, running parallel to the flange, began to emerge. Contrarily, in specimen M90, this yield line was perpendicular, marking a distinct pattern of deformation.

Fig. 9 – von Mises total mechanical strains close to failure a) M0; b) M30; c) M45; d) M90

In the corner of the plate, a prying effect emerged, leading to increased localized pressures in the concrete, exceeding 180 MPa, as shown in Fig. 10, resulting in concrete crushing. These observations align with that of Yang & Kishiki (19), who had previously emphasized that localized pressures in steel-to-concrete connections can surpass seven times the concrete's characteristic strength before leading to crushing.

*White region : Far open contact

Fig. 10 – Contact pressures of the plate on the concrete block at failure a) M0; b) M30; c) M45; d) M90

Having developed a robust numerical model, further numerical investigations that were not feasible experimentally were performed, focusing particularly on the position of the centre of compression in different loading regimes as illustrated in Fig. 11. Notably, for specimen M0, the centre of compression moves away from the flange tip from the onset of loading to failure (at 146.2 mm), closely aligning with the axis of the lower anchor bolts. This finding suggests that the Eurocode's EN1993-1-8 identification of the flange's centre as the centre of compression is overly conservative in the elastic regime (32.3%) and at failure (36.7%) for the actual configuration. In contrast, the centre of compression of the other specimens moved towards the flange tips, a consequence of the non-parallel orientation of the flanges to the bending axis. This orientation induces increased localized pressures on the concrete surface near the lower flange tips, thereby shifting the compression centre closer to the tips. Specifically, in specimens M30 and M45, the centre of compression is located in the vicinity of the welds and moves towards the flange tips at failure. For specimens M0 and M90, the compression centre lies outside the welded area, attributed to a more pronounced yield line in the compressive area.

Fig. 11 – Lever arm in the elastic and plastic regimes of specimens

CONCLUSION

In the present paper, the behaviour of corner-bolted steel-to-concrete end-plate connections was investigated experimentally and numerically, with a focus on the influence of bending moment orientation. The experiments allowed to observe the deformation and failure patterns under four different loading scenarios: in-plane and out-of-plane bending moments as well as biaxial bending moments with an angle of 30 and 45°. The behaviour of the four tested specimens was consistently

similar within the elastic range, showing an average initial rotational stiffness of 4000 kNm/rad. The plastic moments were approximately 78% of the ultimate moments. Failure modes predominantly involved anchor bolt tension failure and end-plate partial yielding, with significant deformations and observable cracking at the weld bases close to the tensile flange tips. A decrease in ultimate moment from specimen M0 to M90 highlighted variations in their elastoplastic behaviour. Under different bending moment orientations, their initial stiffnesses, plastic and ultimate moments mostly followed an elliptical curve. The finite element model enabled to replicate experimental conditions and explore scenarios beyond practical experimentation, particularly in assessing the centre of compression. This research indicates that Eurocode's EN1993-1-8 approach to defining the centre of compression may be too conservative especially in the elastic regime.

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